

(7.7 t ha⁻¹) and on 5 Jul (7.4 t ha⁻¹) in both years (see table). A drastic yield reduction was observed in the 25 Jul planting, but the rate of decrease was slower in 1993 than in 1994. This may be due to the use of aged (40 d) seedlings in 1993. There was 10.1, 4.1, and 57.1% increase in grain yield in the 25 Jun planting over that of 15 Jun, 5 Jul, and 25 July, respectively.

Harvest index and productivity (kg d⁻¹) were highest in the 25 Jun planting, followed by the 5 Jul and 15 Jun plantings.

Lowest values of harvest index and productivity were registered with the 15 Jun planting. Spikelet sterility was lower in 1993. It was similarly lower for 25 Jun and 5 Jul than for 15 Jun and 25 Jul. Percentage sterility was relatively higher for the late planting dates in 1994.

Among genotypes, ORI 161 (PHB71) produced the highest grain yield (7.6 t ha⁻¹). Hybrids ORI 161 and PMS2 A/IR31802 were found significantly superior to

HKR126 (6.5 t ha⁻¹). Productivity and harvest index were highest in ORI 161, followed by PMS2 A/IR3 1802 and HKR126. Spikelet sterility was minimum in ORI 161, followed by HKR126.

Planting hybrid ORI 161 resulted in a 17% increase in grain yield over the best available pureline genotypes. In northwestern India, the best time to transplant hybrid rice is between 25 Jun and 5 Jul. ■

Effect of solar radiation and temperature on rice yields in different planting dates

F. J. Osuna-Canizales, Campo Experimental Zacatepec, Apartado Postal 12, Zacatepec, Morelos 62780, Mexico

Solar radiation and temperature are important climatic factors affecting rice yields under irrigated conditions. In an experiment to define optimum planting dates for the newly released high-yielding variety Morelos A92 and breeding line CAEZ401, the effect of these climatic factors on grain yield was assessed through regression techniques.

Soil is a Vertisol with pH 7.6, 3% organic matter, 0.31% total N, and 22 ppm Olsen P. Five planting dates with

3-wk intervals were evaluated, the first in 29 Apr and the last in 22 Jul 1993.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design at the experimental station of Zacatepec, Morelos with four replications, with planting dates in the main plot and genotypes in the subplots. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were planted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 4- × 4-cm plots. Water management consisted of periodical irrigation. Basal fertilization with 90 kg N ha⁻¹, 40 kg P ha⁻¹, and 40 kg K ha⁻¹ was applied 25 d after transplanting (DAT); additionally, 45 kg N ha⁻¹ each were applied at panicle initiation and at booting stage. Grain yield in a 9-m² area was measured and adjusted to 14% moisture on a wet basis.

Regression analysis with grain yield as the dependent variable and global radiation

(GR, estimated after sunshine hours) and minimum mean temperature (MMT) as independent variables were performed in three periods: from 20 d before flowering up to flowering (f-20), from flowering to 20 d after flowering (f+20), and from 20 d before to 20 d after flowering (f-20 to f+20).

Growth duration was shortened in the last planting dates because of photoperiod sensitivity of the two genotypes (see table). In the first planting date, Morelos A92 and CAEZ401 were harvested 137 and 125 DAT, respectively, whereas in the last planting date, Morelos A92 and CAEZ401 were harvested 120 DAT. Grain yield declined in Morelos A92 as planting was delayed (see figure), but in CAEZ401, decline was significant only for the late planting date.

Regression equations and parameters to assess the fitness of different models in the three periods. Zacatepec, Morelos, Mexico, 1993.

Model	Equation	R ²	(%) ^a	MSE ^b
<i>f-20^c</i>				
1	Yield ^d = 10328 - 4.6 (GR) ^e	0.16	25.9	2909314
2	Yield = 437393 - 49234 (MMT) ^e + 1410 (MMT ²)	0.07	78.1	3670335
3	Yield = 10599 - 93 (GR/MMT)	0.19	20.2	2776786
4	Yield = 916660 + 980 (GR) - 78858 (MMT) + 1496 (MMT ²) - 16751 (GR/MMT)	0.85	2.6	813472
<i>f + 20</i>				
1	Yield = 20 (GR) - 2411	0.20	19.9	2768937
2	Yield = 144952 - 17855 (MMT) + 571 (MMT ²)	0.81	0.3	758453
3	Yield = 12114 - 137 (GR/MMT)	0.02	67.4	3365802
4	Yield = 163592 + 37 (GR) - 18847 (MMT) + 568 (MMT ²) - 652 (GR/MMT)	0.81	4.9	1060182
<i>f - 20 to + 20</i>				
1	Yield = 28 (GR) - 6705	0.25	14.4	2595018
2	Yield = 47782 (MMT) - 1277 (MMT ²) - 437848	0.34	23.2	2594505
3	Yield = 305 (GR/MMT) - 796	0.09	40.2	3138594
4	Yield = 454149 + 367 (GR) - 44589 (MMT) - 1051 (MMT ²) - 6035 (GR/MMT)	0.49	40.9	2799678

^aObserved level of significance. ^bMean square error. ^cf - 20 = from 20 d before flowering up to flowering, f + 20 = from flowering to 20 d after flowering, f - 20 to + 20 = from 20 d before to 20 d after flowering. ^dkg ha⁻¹. ^eGR = global radiation. MMT = mean minimum temperature.

Effect of planting date on grain yield of cultivar Morelos A92 and breeding line CAEZ401. Zacatepec, Morelos, Mexico. 1993.

Filled grains panicle⁻¹ and grain weight were the most affected by late transplanting. For the two genotypes, filled grains panicle⁻¹ went down from 63 in the first date to 47 in the last date while 1,000 grain weight was reduced from 43.6 to 40.7 g.

The regression equations obtained and the parameters used to evaluate fitness of the models in each period are shown in the table. Within each period, the best fit was obtained when GR and MMT were

evaluated together (model 4), except in the period f+20, when MMT and MMT2 (model 2) were comparable. The fitness of model 4 was higher for f-20 and f+20 than their combination.

These results show that variation in incident global radiation and mean minimum temperature during the period 20 d before or 20 d after flowering may explain much of the variation in grain yield in the different planting dates for irrigated rice. ■

Integrated pest management—diseases

Effects of neem derivatives on sheath rot in scented rice

K. Sivaprakasam and R. Jagannathan, Plant Pathology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India

We assessed the efficacy of botanical biocides and pesticides (fungicides carbendazim and mancozeb) for controlling sheath rot (ShR) of scented rice. Leaf extract and fungicides were applied twice as foliar sprays at a 2-wk interval beginning at booting. The field trial was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications using scented hybrid rice JJ92. Plot size was 5 × 2 m.

ShR incidence was measured as the percentage of infected tillers in 25

Comparison of biocides to control sheath rot incidence and grain yield of scented rice JJ92.

Treatment	Percent ShR incidence ^a	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
Neem oil (3%)	30.22 (33.25)	5.2
Neem seed kernel extract (5%)	26.30 (29.70)	5.0
Monocrotophos (1250 ml ha ⁻¹)	25.86 (30.48)	4.4
Carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	24.27 (29.80)	4.1
Mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	30.47 (33.38)	3.4
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + carbendazim (500 g ha ⁻¹)	27.57 (31.61)	3.8
Monocrotophos (1250 ml) + mancozeb (1 kg ha ⁻¹)	22.87 (28.49)	4.5
Nochi (10%) (<i>Vitex negundo</i>)	26.80 (31.10)	4.2
Untreated check	37.52 (37.67)	3.2
LSD (P=0.05)	1.10	.5

^aMeans of three replications. Data in parentheses are arcsine-transformed values.

randomly selected hills/plot 20 d after the last spray. Higher yields were recorded with neem oil (3%), neem seed kernel extract (5%), and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹) + mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹). Standard fungicides carbendazim (500 g ha⁻¹) and monocrotophos (1,250 ml ha⁻¹), and

mancozeb (1 kg ha⁻¹) effectively reduced ShR incidence (see table).

Using a spray of neem seed kernel extract generated higher grain yield and effectively reduced disease incidence, although to a lesser degree, than using regular fungicides. ■

Seed borne nature and seed transmission of rice sheath blight

S. Acharya and P. K. S. Gupta, Plant Pathology Department, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya (BCKV), Kalyani 741235, Nadia, West Bengal, India

Although rice sheath blight (ShB) caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* is documented as a seedborne disease, evidence of this nature is lacking. We investigated spotted and apparently healthy seeds of rice cultivar Swarna Mashuri to find out the mode of transmission involved. The seeds were collected from a heavily ShB-infected rice crop from the BCKV Regional Research Farm.

Effect of *R. solani* infection on rice germination and seed health. West Bengal^a, India.

Treatment	Seeds yielding <i>R. solani</i> (%)	Germination (%)	Seedling infection (%)	Seedling collapse (%)	Shoot fresh weight (mg)	Shoot dry weight (mg)	Root fresh weight (mg)	Root dry weight (mg)
Naturally Infested seeds	37.83	59.09	14.88	4.35	279.46	46.83	485.7	64.1
Artificially inoculated seeds	56.35	70.66	23.58	9.21	361.20	66.05	673.75	120.13
Apparently healthy seeds	12.17	73.19	0	0	467.26	94.3	922.4	174.3
SE ±	0.682	0.655	0.728	0.127	0.57	0.376	0.575	0.324
LSD (0.05)	1.520	1.459	1.624	0.284	1.286	0.838	1.281	0.721
Unsterilized seeds	50.92	65.63	8.70	9.09	334.66	60.52	608.66	109
Surface-sterilized seeds	19.98	69.67	6.93	0	403.94	77.60	779.23	130.02
SE ±	0.545	0.535	0.594	0.018	0.47	0.307	0.469	0.265
LSD (0.05)	1.214	1.19	1.326	0.024	1.050	0.684	1.04	0.590
Interaction								
SE ±	0.9315	0.9266	1.03	0.032	0.81	0.532	0.813	0.459
LSD (0.05)	2.07	2.06	2.29	0.072	1.819	1.85	1.81	1.022

^aAll percentage data are transformed angular values.